

INTRODUCTION TO ORGANIC CHEMISTRY

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Annotation. Modern methods of teaching bioorganic chemistry (working with a textbook, reproductive, heuristic, problem situation, research, project method, case-study method, lecture, story, interview methods, practical training, laboratory work), methods of drawing conclusions (induction, deduction and analytical method) Due to the 2 hours allocated to the lesson, special individual skills are required to deliver complete information. The use of the "Case-study" method in the training opens up a number of opportunities for delivering the information available in the database to students.

Key words: reproductive, heuristic, problem situation, research, project method, case-study method

Introduction. "Case-study" is an English word ("case" - specific situation, event, "study" - to study, analyze) is a method aimed at carrying out teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations. In a case, open information or a specific event can be used as a situation for analysis.

This method, unlike problem-based learning, is based on making clear decisions based on the study of real situations. If it is used as a way to achieve a certain goal in the educational process, it has the character of a method, if it is carried out step by step in the study of a process, based on a certain algorithm, it reflects a technological aspect.

Work stage: 1st stage: "Introduction to organic (bioorganic) chemistry. Information supply of the topic "Classification and general properties of organic compounds". The introduction is a brief introduction to the subject. It can be presented to students in the form of a presentation. Because it provides general information that is familiar to OO'Yu students. Information in textual and media form is included in all the specified issues.

Issues to consider:

1. "Tasks of bioorganic chemistry": a brief presentation is given in the form of text or media, since the student has a preliminary understanding, because this question also contains general information.

2. Covering "Biopolymers, groups of biocontrollers" is slightly different from the first one, because students of the 1st year are not yet familiar with biopolymers and biocontrollers

(bioregulators). So a slightly different approach is needed for students to master the concept, but in questions 2 and beyond, an additional database is needed. Biopolymers and bioregulators are high molecular compounds (UMB) found directly in living organisms. So, the student should be able to perform audio-visual work individually, i.e. listen to the lecture and record the necessary information, get acquainted with the case, understand the textual media, be able to summarize the information, i.e. understand the structure, existence, function of these substances in the body, be able to analyze the received information, and finally solve the problem being studied (information to be understood).

3. "Chemical structure, configuration and conformation" and "Types of isomerism: structural isomerism and stereoisomerism, types of stereoisomerism: enantiomerism, racemates, diastereomerism" can be used for the presentation and presentation of modules and computer animations representing the spatial structure of substances. In addition to knowing the spatial structure of substances found in the body, the student should understand that their activity depends on their spatial structure. For example, if we take any UMB, their spatial structure is important in the organism, because the mutation (change in configuration or conformation) of these substances as a result of external influence directly affects the metabolism and synthesis of substances.

Conclusion. Formulation and justification of the case solution, presentation. In this case, the solution is worked out individually or in groups. The possibilities of practical application of alternatives are substantiated, a creative-project presentation is prepared (for example, the study of the structure of organic substances used as medicinal substances and the chemical basis of their action), the final conclusion and the practical aspects of the solution of the situation are highlighted.

At the end of the lecture, the students will be given the addresses of the Internet sites in order to fully master the subject.

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